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The Challenges of Communism in Bihar: Analyzing Ideological Stagnation and Political Ineffectiveness in a Complex Social Landscape

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Abstract:

The communist movement in Bihar has struggled to make a significant impact on the state's socio-political landscape, despite its historical roots and ideological potential. This paper critically examines the reasons behind the stagnation and ineffectiveness of various communist parties in Bihar, focusing on their failure to adapt to the changing social, economic, and political dynamics of the region. The study highlights how the communists' outdated focus on feudalism, disregard for the rise of capitalism, and inability to address key issues such as unemployment, migration, and social welfare have alienated them from the masses. Furthermore, the fragmented nature of communist factions and their reluctance to engage with local caste and community structures have further diminished their influence. In contrast, other political formations in Bihar, such as the BJP, RJD, and JD(U), have successfully leveraged caste and community equations to gain power. This paper argues that the communists' lack of vision, coupled with their refusal to embrace modern economic realities, has rendered them irrelevant in the current political discourse of Bihar.

Keywords: Communism in Bihar; Ideological Stagnation of the Left; Political Ineffectiveness of the Left; Society and Communism in Bihar.

Full text:

The Communist parties in India have often struggled to achieve meaningful success due to a lack of clear vision and effective methods for societal and governmental improvement. Their approach frequently appeared confused and unproductive, failing to yield significant results. Despite speaking out against feudalism, they overlooked the fact that feudalism had largely collapsed and instead labeled certain social groups or castes that did not align with their ideologies as feudal, without addressing the rise of new capitalist structures in society.

One of the central issues with the Communist parties, especially in regions like Bihar, was their tendency to incite social conflicts rather than focusing on constructive programs and policies for the welfare of the people. They often engaged with governments for personal or communal gain rather than for the public good. Although they spoke about the plight of the poor, their approach often targeted specific social groups, which essentially amounted to caste politics. This narrow focus caused them to overlook major social, political, economic, and religious issues in Bihar, such as unemployment, migration, land and water management, productivity, law and order, leadership, corruption, education, public health, and social security.

As a result, the Communist parties failed to create a significant impact or build confidence among any substantial section of Bihar's population. They operated through communes or syndicates but did not engage with the diverse social structure of Bihar, failing to connect with various castes, communities, and other social categories. Although they advocated for labor rights, they did not adequately address the concerns of farmers, nor did they adapt to the reality that feudalism had ended post-independence. This approach reflected a caste-based attitude influenced by the Brahmanical leadership within the Congress party.

Communist opposition to development, neoliberalism, and modernization was inconsistent, as they did not effectively challenge liberalization, privatization, and globalization. They neither understood the micro-level social structures nor integrated the changes imposed by macro-level social institutions. Moreover, they failed to present their ideas about social institutions, particularly those related to the economy and the state and remained silent on key systems such as education, politics, and the economy. Despite having ideas for societal improvement, they were unable to effectively communicate these to the masses.

In contrast, newer political formations in Bihar, such as the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Rashtriya Janata Dal (RJD), and Janata Dal United (JD-U), have gained power by successfully navigating caste and community dynamics. Even smaller parties like the Lok Janshakti Party (LJP), Hindustani Awam Morcha (HAM), and Rashtriya Lok Samta Party (RLSP) have outperformed the Communist parties by effectively engaging with the electorate. These parties' electoral successes can largely be attributed to their understanding and manipulation of caste and community equations.

While the RSS and Congress also operated through communes, the political success of both the Congress and BJP was not solely due to their organizational structures but because they actively engaged with social issues. For example, the Congress promoted secularism, while the BJP focused on corruption and minority appeasement. In contrast, the Communists remained aloof, disconnected from the broader political discourse.

The Communist parties in Bihar, particularly, suffered from fragmentation, with multiple factions and ideologies confusing the electorate. This disunity, coupled with their reluctance to address significant social issues like Ayodhya, Kashi, Mathura, reservations, Kashmir, and the declining Hindu population, further alienated them from the people. They attempted to portray themselves as moral and intellectual, but their mobilization efforts often involved unethical practices, such as bribing participants for rallies and meetings. This lack of integrity, combined with their disconnection from castes, communities, and categories of people, weakened their position.

The Communists' failure to adapt their progressive ideology to the needs and concerns of the people was a significant weakness. Their ideas about a stateless society, labor unity, and institutional critiques were ineffective without popular support. The public was more concerned with solving their immediate problems than with lofty ideological slogans. Even though the Communists, like the RSS, provided a platform for discussing issues in society, they failed to address core concerns such as wage disparities, which could have bridged the gap between different social classes.

The Communist parties could have advocated for wage uniformity across different types of work, whether in the public or private sector, which might have reduced the allure of government jobs and encouraged people to pursue other livelihoods. They could have promoted societal approaches to education, health, welfare, justice, and internal-external security. Moreover, they missed the opportunity to lead efforts to dismantle religious and caste boundaries, which could have united people across the subcontinent.

Over time, the Communists' failure to deliver on their promises and their lack of seriousness about the people's needs led to their decline. They could not forge strong partnerships with castes and communities in Bihar, nor did they inspire hope for improvement in agriculture, industry, employment, or self-employment. Their inability to engage with the business community and market forces further eroded their influence.

In contrast, other nations, such as China, successfully adapted their policies to embrace market economies, even as they maintained a Communist political structure. This pragmatism has allowed China to thrive, while India's Communist parties have struggled to find a place in the rapidly changing socio-economic landscape. The rise of naxalism, Maoism, international terrorism, Hindu fundamentalism, and judicial-social activism can all be seen as reactions to the broader forces of globalization, market economy, and liberalization, particularly as influenced by the USA and China.

The Communist parties in India are also fragmented into multiple formations, such as the Communist Party of India (CPI), Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPI-M), Communist Party of India (Maoist) Liberation (CPI-ML), and various underground revolutionary groups like the Maoist Communist Centre (MCC), People's Liberation Front of India (PLFI), and Party Unity, among others. These factions have only contributed to the confusion among the public regarding their ideologies and capabilities. While some student wings like the All-India Students Federation (AISF) and All India Students Association

(AISA) have managed to maintain a presence on university campuses, raising social and political issues, the broader Communist movement has largely failed to resonate with the public.

The lack of association with the local social structure, such as caste and community, has been a major reason for the Communists' failure in Bihar. Political objectives cannot be achieved without addressing the local social structures, problems, and solutions.

The Communists also failed to support market and neoliberal policies, which are modern-day realities tied to industrialization and urbanization. Their undemocratic behavior further alienated them from the people, as they focused on sharing the produce without addressing productivity improvements. Their actions often contradicted their high moral rhetoric, which caused the public to lose trust in them.

Historically, the 1930s saw the rise of a significant peasant (Kisan) movement in the central Gangetic plain, comprising modern-day eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. Politicians from all spectrums, from right to left, emphasized the importance of this group's participation in the freedom struggle against British rule. This period also saw a surge in Hindi publications and colonial documents reporting Kisan agitations, which were often feared as signs of Bolshevism.

While the emergence of the Kisan as a politically, economically, and socially significant category under colonial rule was driven by a long historical process, it is often mistakenly attributed solely to pro-peasant discourses of the time. In reality, this development was shaped by broader socio-economic conditions and colonial policies.

In the context of peasant studies, the Communists' approach, heavily influenced by Marxist thought, often overlooked the complexity of the peasant class and its potential role in revolutionary movements. While Karl Marx himself gave less significance to peasants, seeing them as incapable of revolutionary initiative, Mao Zedong later recognized the importance of different classes within the peasantry in China, which contributed to revolutionary success.

In India, however, the Communists failed to effectively mobilize the peasantry or recognize their role in a broader socio-economic context. Despite the rise of peasant movements in the 1930s, the Communists were unable to harness this energy into a successful revolutionary force. The rigid application of Marxist theory often clashed with the realities on the ground, leading to a disconnect between Communist ideologies and the needs of the people.

In conclusion, the Communist parties in India, particularly in regions like Bihar, have struggled due to a combination of factors, including a lack of clear vision, failure to adapt to changing socio-economic conditions, and a disconnection from local social structures. Their inability to engage effectively with the public, coupled with internal fragmentation, has led to their decline in influence. Meanwhile, other political formations have successfully navigated the complex socio-political landscape, gaining power and influence by addressing the immediate concerns of the people.

Kapil Kumar's more stringent application of class analysis leads him to conclude that the Kisan Sabha movement can be defined as a class struggle of poor peasants and landless laborers against landlords. He challenges the middle peasant thesis proposed by Hamza Alavi and Eric Wolf, which suggests that poor peasants take the path to revolution only when they perceive the power of landlords as breakable and when an alternative existence seems possible. Unlike Siddiqi, Kumar argues that the Non-Cooperation Movement, led primarily by the urban middle class and landlords, aimed to restrain the Kisan Sabha from adopting a more radical approach. He also emphasizes the impact of the First World War on rural society, including the participation of demobilized soldiers in the movement and the economic hardships it caused.

Dhanagare similarly critiques the middle peasant thesis by examining peasant movements in the United Provinces during the interwar years. He demonstrates that each movement was linked to specific social conditions, with different agrarian sections participating based on their unique circumstances. For example, he agrees with Kumar that poor peasants and landless laborer, who were burdened by rising rents and prices during the war, were the primary participants in the Kisan Sabha movement. Conversely, he characterizes the no-rent campaign of the early 1930s, conducted under the Civil Disobedience Movement, as primarily involving rich and middle peasants. These groups, more connected to the market economy, were severely affected by the Great Depression and thus drove the movement. However, due to their vested interests, the campaign did not evolve into a broader struggle involving lower strata, highlighting the limited radical potential of the richer peasants.

Rajendra Singh underscores the significance of external political leadership in shaping peasant movements in the U.P. after the 1930s. In his study of tenant struggles in Basti, he argues that the involvement of local Congress leaders, with their modern education and political experience, provided peasants with organized strategies and class consciousness. This shift enabled peasants to perceive structural contradictions and contemplate alternatives for the first time.

Moving eastward, the Champaran Satyagraha and Kisan Sabha in Bihar have been central topics in scholarly debates. Most studies on Bihar emphasize the continuity of traditional forms of resistance, which were limited in their ability to bring about structural change. Scholars have noted the role of intermediary groups that bridged the gap between insurgent peasants and elite leaders. These intermediaries, often small landlords or better-off peasants, wielded significant social, economic, and political influence at the village level. Consequently, peasant movements in Bihar did not fundamentally alter the social structure, and the control of peasants by local elites remains a key issue.

Jacques Pouchepadass, in his analysis of the Champaran Satyagraha, describes it as largely a traditional resistance movement, with well-off peasants and trader-moneylenders from upper castes playing active roles. These leaders mobilized poorer peasants using intimidation, social boycotts, and religious symbols—tactics familiar from earlier anti-planter resistances. However, he also highlights the mediating role of local notables, such as mukhtars and schoolmasters, who connected the masses with urban intellectuals, transforming the movement into a broader contestation of the Champaran indigo plantation system.

Stephen Henningham also focuses on the role of local notables in north Bihar's peasant movements between 1917 and 1942. He argues that these movements primarily aligned with the anti-colonial struggle and rarely took the form of full-scale anti-feudal or anti-landlord struggles. This pattern persisted because the Congress, particularly in Bihar, relied on the support of village elites—often small landlords and rich peasants—who carefully avoided conflicts that could threaten their interests. These elites, in turn, exerted pressure on the British Raj while consolidating their power in local government structures, such as district authorities and municipal boards. Henningham concludes that the British policy of maintaining the traditional social structure, supported by landlords and acquiesced to by village elites, was crucial in preventing more radical movements.

Anand Yang provides a long historical perspective on Henningham's argument, examining the collaborative relationships between British rulers and indigenous elites in the Saran district. He identifies a "multi-fold structure" of local control, where both supra-village level landlords and village-level controllers—often from higher social status groups—maintained their dominance from the pre-colonial period, as long as they served the superior authority's interests. Under this "Limited Raj," peasants' options for resistance were limited to minor or negative actions, such as desertion, seasonal migration, or petty crimes, rather than sustained and open conflicts. Even when tensions between peasants and landlords erupted, these movements rarely escalated into broader struggles, reflecting the limited capacity of rich and middle peasants to lead more radical movements.

William L. Rowe analyzes a caste mobility movement among the Chauhans (also known as Noniya, Nuniya, Loniya, or Luniya) in the Benares district, tracing its development from the late nineteenth century to the present. This movement appears to have successfully elevated the Chauhans' social status, at least in the village he studied. According to Rowe, the community improved its position in the village's caste hierarchy, moving from "almost untouchable" to ninth or tenth out of twenty-four castes, thereby rising above the untouchable line. Rowe examines the relationship between ritual and economic status, concluding that the movement was driven by a discrepancy between their low ritual status and their improving economic conditions.

In the early stages of the movement, the Chauhan community, whose economic position was relatively modest, faced attacks from ritually and politically dominant Kshatriya landlords. These local conflicts, deeply connected to the interests of the majority, had significant social impacts. In the central Gangetic Plain, growing concerns about caste identity and aspirations for higher status became evident among major cultivating castes like the Yadavs and Kurmis, who were demographically strong and considered "middle" in the caste hierarchy. From the early 20th century, these middle-ranking cultivating castes began reorganizing themselves and seeking higher status. They established broader social and geographical organizations, or "caste sabhas," which advocated for their economic, social, and political interests before the colonial authorities and guided their members in social reform. This social mobility

movement among the middle castes sparked numerous conflicts with upper castes, who had traditionally held superior positions in society.

A closer examination of these conflicts reveals an inseparable link between social and economic status. These disputes often had an economic dimension, with relationships between upper castes and middle cultivating castes frequently translating into landlord-tenant dynamics, thereby contributing to the class formation of the peasantry. This study fundamentally addresses the transformation of peasant formations under conditions shaped and solidified by colonial rule.

Class as a Historical 'Happening'

As noted by scholars such as William Pinch and Susan Bayly, the peasant movements that emerged and characterized popular uprisings in the 1930s were significantly influenced by earlier caste movements. However, the historical significance of these caste movements for later peasant movements is not always clearly articulated. Sekhar Bandyopadhyay provides a meticulous account of the Namasudras, a group that gradually took up cultivation and reconstructed their self-image, transitioning from being called "Chandals" to "Namasudras." His study illustrates how this severely oppressed community, much lower in status than the Yadavs and Kurmis in the central Gangetic Plain, organized themselves into a middle peasantry in rural East Bengal. While Bandyopadhyay's work is highly relevant, this study focuses on a more dynamic case of class formation involving various communities, with particular emphasis on local conflicts between middle and upper castes. These conflicts played a significant role in fostering class consciousness among cultivators.

Because caste-based conflicts often involved economic issues such as land ownership, illegal cesses, and forced labor imposed by zamindars, middle castes were provided opportunities to understand their relations with both socially and economically superior upper castes. E. P. Thompson's statement is particularly relevant here: "When discussing a class, one finds oneself too frequently commencing sentences with 'it.' It is time to place oneself under some historical control, or one is in danger of becoming the slave of one's categories." Thompson argues that class is not a static entity, but a dynamic social and cultural formation that is defined through relationships with other classes, and can only be understood in terms of action, reaction, change, and conflict.

This study will detail how the experiences of local conflicts among various castes led to the development of class consciousness and the emergence of the peasantry, or "Kisan," as a class in the 1930s. Although the Kisan Sabha movement in Oudh resembled a class-based peasant movement, a detailed analysis of landlord-tenant relations will show that these relationships were also shaped by caste lines, and disturbances in these relations often confirmed this.

Kisan Sabha movements in Bihar during the 1930s and the preceding caste movements shared common features, including continuity in their organization, mode of action, and the issues they addressed. For example, Swami Sahajanand's account of the Kisan Sabha's origins and the high proportion of Bhumihar members in its leadership suggests a close connection with the Bhumihar Brahman Sabha. Despite shifting from arbitration to a more confrontational stance against zamindars and beginning the Bakasht struggle after 1936, this continuity remained. As this study will reveal, the experience of caste movements was carried into the Kisan Sabha movement, maintaining a significant influence.

The strong presence of specific castes in major peasant movements, such as the Kurmis in the Kisan Sabha movement of Oudh, the Bhumihars in Bihar's Kisan Sabha, and the Goalas, Koeris, and Kurmis in the Triveni Sangh, can be understood in the context of middle caste groups rising socially and politically through a long process of ideological and economic empowerment. However, it is unlikely that a chronological order exists between caste and peasant movements, as some Marxist historians suggest, at least during the first half of the 20th century in the central Gangetic Plain. As this study will demonstrate, there was little change in the economic order of castes throughout the colonial period.

Nevertheless, cracks within the peasant class were always present, undermining its unity. The Bihar Provincial Kisan Sabha, in its 1936 manifesto, defined itself as representing not only tenants but also small zamindars and agricultural laborers. This inclusivity made it difficult to manage tenant struggles within the estates of small zamindars. In disputes between small zamindars and tenants, particularly where power differences were minimal, the conflicts often echoed caste struggles from before the 1920s.

At the lower end of the peasant class, another division became increasingly apparent by the late 1930s. Legislative measures that enhanced the legal position of occupancy raiyats and improved their social

status as middle castes widened the socioeconomic gap between them and under-raiyats or agricultural laborers, who typically belonged to lower social strata and lacked sufficient legal protection. A typical example of this issue is found among the Santhal bataidars in the Kosi Diara area of the Purnea district, where disputes arose between tenure-holders and Santhal bataidars, or between Goala bidders and Santhal bataidars. In the 1940s, the class of Kisan as a historical "happening" began to erode as divisions among sections of the Kisan class widened. However, this process also marked the beginning of a new phase for those sections of the Kisan class that entered the next round of historical developments.

Conclusion:

The communist movement in Bihar, once a potent force for social change, has faltered due to a combination of outdated ideologies, internal fragmentation, and a disconnection from the region's social realities. By continuing to focus on a defunct feudal system, failing to recognize the rise of new capitalist dynamics, and neglecting pressing issues like unemployment and social security, the communists have become marginalized. Moreover, their reluctance to engage with local caste and community structures has prevented them from forming meaningful alliances that could have broadened their support base. As a result, newer political formations that effectively navigate caste and community politics have eclipsed the communists in Bihar's political landscape. For the communist movement to regain relevance, it must reassess its strategies, address contemporary socio-economic challenges, and forge stronger connections with the local populace. Without these changes, the communist parties in Bihar risk continuing their decline into political obscurity.

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